

OUT-OF-PLANE DEFORMATION BEHAVIOUR OF MULTI-LAYER PAPERBOARD SUBJECTED TO TRANSIENT MOISTURE DIFFUSION

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SUMMARY

An analytical method to predict the through-thickness moisture content and associated induced deformations of paperboard sheets subjected to relative humidity changes is presented. Out-of-plane deformations are predicted as a function of time. Comparisons with steady-state analyses reveal major differences in the shape of one cardboard sheet.

Keywords: laminate, hygro-mechanical, Ritz method, transient, warping.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the last decade, dimensional instability and curl of paper and cardboard have become an important issue for the pulp and paper industry. Several studies have been conducted to better understand the problem and propose strategies to increase the dimensional stability of paper sheets.

The moisture-induced deformation of paper has been the subject of several studies. Nordstrom et al. [1] and Gendron et al. [2] studied the behaviour of paper and cardboard sheets subjected to humidity change using a Rayleigh-Ritz approach similar to the one that Hyer [3] used to study the response of unsymmetric laminates to thermal loading. They also performed steady-state geometrically non linear finite-element analyses. Lu and Carlsson [4] investigated the effect of viscoelastic stress relaxation on the curl response of paper subjected to transient humidity change. They concluded that a model which takes the moisture diffusion process through the thickness into account would lead to more accurate predictions. However, this has not yet been achieved.

This study focuses on predicting the transient response of paper or cardboard sheets subjected to through-thickness moisture diffusion. The objective is to study the development of curl during the moisture diffusion process. To achieve this objective, the through-thickness moisture content distribution is predicted as a function of time and, for each time increment, the moisture-induced deformation is computed. As multiple equilibrium configurations were expected, a semi-analytical approach, such as the one proposed by Hyer [3], was used as it would give more insight into the curl response than using a finite-element model. However, the finite-element software ABAQUS is used to validate the predictions of the semi-analytical model.

2. MODEL DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Moisture content distribution prediction

The model is developed for a paper or a cardboard sheet made of N -layers as shown in Fig. 1. Each layer is assumed to have a constant density ρ_i and an effective diffusion coefficient D_i ($i=1, \dots, N$). The sheet is initially ($t = 0$) in equilibrium with air at a relative humidity RH_0 . The sheet has a uniform moisture content M_0 . Suddenly, at $t = 0$, the ambient relative humidity changes to RH_∞ and the sheet is subjected to moisture flux through both boundary surfaces, at $z = z_0$ and $z = z_N$. After the sheet reaches equilibrium, the moisture content is equal to M_∞ . Since the sheet thickness is small relative to its length and width, it is reasonable to assume that moisture movement occurs exclusively in the z -direction. The moisture transport process is treated as a diffusion problem based on Fick's second law [5]. The transient moisture movement can be expressed using the diffusion equation formulated in a one dimensional space by

$$\frac{\partial^2 \theta_i}{\partial z^2} = \frac{1}{D_i} \frac{\partial \theta_i}{\partial t}, \quad z \in [z_{i-1}, z_i], \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad (1)$$

where $\theta_i = \theta_i(z, t) = M_\infty - M_i(z, t)$ is the difference in moisture content between the equilibrium moisture content at RH_∞ and the moisture content in the i th-layer, at position z and time t . The initial condition (at $t = 0$) specifies that the initial moisture content is uniform and equal to M_0 . It can be expressed as

$$\theta_i(z, t = 0) = \theta_0, \quad z \in [z_{i-1}, z_i], \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad (2)$$

where $\theta_0 = M_\infty - M_0$ is the difference in moisture content between the equilibrium moisture content at RH_∞ and the initial moisture content. For $t > 0$, both boundary surfaces of the sheet are subjected to convective moisture flux which can be expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} -k_1 \left(\frac{\partial \theta_1}{\partial z} \right)_{z_0} + h_0 \theta_1(z_0, t) &= 0 \\ k_N \left(\frac{\partial \theta_N}{\partial z} \right)_{z_N} + h_N \theta_N(z_N, t) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $k_1 = D_1 \rho_1 / 100$ and $k_N = D_N \rho_N / 100$ are the effective diffusivity coefficients of the first and N th-layers, respectively. Quantities h_0 and h_N are the convective mass transfer coefficients for the outer surface at $z = z_0$ and the outer surface at $z = z_N$, respectively. They are assumed to be uniform and constant. The contact between adjacent layers is assumed to be perfect. Therefore, the moisture content and the moisture flux are continuous at the surface of two adjacent layers which can be expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_i(z_i, t) &= \theta_{i+1}(z_i, t) \\ k_i \left(\frac{\partial \theta_i}{\partial z} \right)_{z_i} &= k_{i+1} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_{i+1}}{\partial z} \right)_{z_i} \quad i = 1, \dots, N-1, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $k_i = D_i \rho_i / 100$ is the effective diffusivity coefficient of the i th-layer.

Fig. 1 Representation of a multi-layer paper or cardboard sheet

Equations (1)-(4) can be solved using the “natural” analytic technique proposed by de Monte [6] for solving transient heat conduction in a multi-layer composite laminate. When separating the variables, the effective moisture diffusion coefficient D_i of each layer is retained on the side of the modified moisture diffusion equation where the time-dependent functions are collected. It results in a transcendental equation for the determination of the eigenvalues that are simpler than the ones obtained when using traditional techniques. It was felt that numerous derivations of the equations that lead to the solution were not necessary as they are all indicated in [6]. Using this approach, the solution of the set of equations can be written as,

$$\theta_i(z, t) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} s_m \phi_{i,m} \tilde{Z}_{i,m}(z) e^{-\lambda_m^2 D_i t}, \quad z \in [z_{i-1}, z_i], \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad (5)$$

where s_m is given by,

$$s_m = \frac{\theta_0}{N_m} \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_{i,m} \left(\frac{k_i}{D_i} \right) \left\{ - \left[\frac{\tilde{Z}'_{i,m}(z)}{\lambda_m^2 (D_1/D_i)} \right]_{z_{i-1}}^{z_i} \right\}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N. \quad (6)$$

In Eqs. (5) and (6), $\phi_{i,m}$ are functions defined in [6], λ_m is the m th eigenvalue, $\tilde{Z}_{i,m}(z)$ is the m th eigenfunction corresponding to the m th eigenvalue λ_m in the i th layer and N_m is the normalization integral (norm) associated with the m th eigenvalue λ_m . Substituting the definitions of the moisture content difference $\theta_i(z, t) = M_\infty - M_i(z, t)$ and $\theta_0 = M_\infty - M_0$ into Eqs. (5) and (6) and rearranging the terms lead to

$$M_i(z, t) = M_\infty - (M_\infty - M_0) \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{N_m} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_{i,m} \left(\frac{k_i}{D_i} \right) \left[\frac{\tilde{Z}'_{i,m}(z)}{\lambda_m^2 (D_1/D_i)} \right]_{z_{i-1}}^{z_i} \right\} \phi_{i,m} \tilde{Z}_{i,m}(z) e^{-\lambda_m^2 D_i t} \quad (7)$$

$$z \in [z_{i-1}, z_i], \quad i = 1, \dots, N$$

which gives the distribution of the moisture content through the thickness of the N -layer sheet.

The software *MATHEMATICA*[®] was used to compute and solve the set of equations. The number p of eigenvalues used in the series solution, Eq. (7), was set to 30. This number was selected because it offered a good compromise between accuracy of the approximate solution and reasonable computation time.

The obtained solution gives the moisture content as a function of time and the z -coordinate for each layer. Since the expression is quite complex, it will require lengthy computation if it is directly used to compute moisture induced-deformations. Therefore, the solution obtained for each layer was approximated for given times t_p by a piecewise-linear function of the form

$$M_{lin,i,j}(z) = M_i(z_{i,j-1}, t_p) + \left(\frac{M_i(z_{i,j}, t_p) - M_i(z_{i,j-1}, t_p)}{z_{i,j} - z_{i,j-1}} \right) z, \quad j=1, \dots, J \quad (8)$$

where J is the number of intervals in each layer, $z_{i,j-1}$ and $z_{i,j}$ are the coordinates of the j th interval of the i th layer. Hence, the moisture content distribution for a N -layer sheet at $t = t_p$ can be expressed as

$$M_{lin}(z) = M_{lin,i,j}(z), \quad z_{i,j-1} \leq z \leq z_{i,j}, \quad i=1, \dots, N, \quad j=1, \dots, J. \quad (9)$$

2.2 Moisture-induced deformation prediction

Once the moisture content distribution can be predicted for a particular time $t = t_p$, the associated moisture-induced deformation may be calculated. The model developed to predict the response of a multi-layer paper or cardboard sheet to a through-thickness moisture content distribution is based on Hyer's approach [3].

Assuming a state of plane-stress, the total potential energy of the multi-layer sheet, Π , can be expressed as a function of material and geometric properties of the sheet, moisture content change ΔM , and the total strains by

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi = & \frac{1}{2} \int_{-L_x/2}^{L_x/2} \int_{-L_y/2}^{L_y/2} \int_{-H/2}^{H/2} \left(\frac{1}{2} \bar{Q}_{11} \varepsilon_x^2 + \bar{Q}_{12} \varepsilon_y \varepsilon_x + \bar{Q}_{16} \gamma_{xy} \varepsilon_x + \frac{1}{2} \bar{Q}_{22} \varepsilon_y^2 + \bar{Q}_{26} \gamma_{xy} \varepsilon_y \right. \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \bar{Q}_{66} \gamma_{xy}^2 - (\bar{Q}_{11} \alpha_x + \bar{Q}_{12} \alpha_y + \bar{Q}_{16} \alpha_{xy}) \varepsilon_x \Delta M - (\bar{Q}_{12} \alpha_x + \bar{Q}_{22} \alpha_y + \bar{Q}_{26} \alpha_{xy}) \varepsilon_y \Delta M \\ & \left. - (\bar{Q}_{16} \alpha_x + \bar{Q}_{26} \alpha_y + \bar{Q}_{66} \alpha_{xy}) \gamma_{xy} \Delta M \right) dx dy dz, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where L_x , L_y , and H are the lengths of the sheet in the x - and y -directions, and its thickness. The \bar{Q}_{ij} terms are the transformed reduced stiffness of the individual layer. Using the piecewise-linear function defined by Eq. (9), the change in moisture content ΔM can be expressed at a particular time $t = t_p$ as

$$\Delta M(z) = M_{lin}(z) - M_0. \quad (11)$$

This equation applies the moisture content distribution determined by the moisture diffusion model at time $t = t_p$ so that the deformation induced by the moisture content change can be calculated.

The total strains ε_x , ε_y , γ_{xy} are given by

$$\varepsilon_x = \varepsilon_x^0 + z \kappa_x \quad \varepsilon_y = \varepsilon_y^0 + z \kappa_y \quad \gamma_{xy} = \gamma_{xy}^0 + z \kappa_{xy} \quad (12)$$

The quantities ε_x^0 , ε_y^0 , γ_{xy}^0 and κ_x , κ_y , κ_{xy} are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x^0 &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x} \right)^2 & \varepsilon_y^0 &= \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w^0}{\partial y} \right)^2 & \gamma_{xy}^0 &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial y} \\ \kappa_x &= -\frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial x^2} & \kappa_y &= -\frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial y^2} & \kappa_{xy} &= -2 \frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial x \partial y}, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where the u^0 , v^0 , and w^0 are the displacements of the midplane in the x -, y -, and z -directions. Note that in the above equation the geometric nonlinearities in the sense of von Karman are included. The displacement components are approximated using the following polynomials

$$\begin{aligned} u^0(x, y) &= cx - a^2 x^3 / 6 - abx y^2 / 4 \\ v^0(x, y) &= dy - b^2 y^3 / 6 - aby x^2 / 4 \\ w^0(x, y) &= 1/2(ax^2 + by^2) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where the coordinates x and y are measured from the geometric center of the initially flat sheet. In these equations, parameters a and b represent the negative of the curvatures in the x - and y -directions, respectively. Parameters c and d represent the portion of the strains in the x - and y -directions that are constant.

Back-substituting the assumed displacements into the definition of the midplane strains and curvatures, Eq. (13), and into the total potential energy expression, Eq. (10), the spatial integrations over x and y can be carried out. Finally, the moisture content change function, Eq. (11), can be substituted into Eq. (10) and the spatial integration over z can be calculated. The final result is an algebraic expression for Π of the form

$$\Pi = \Pi(a, b, c, d), \quad (15)$$

which is valid for a particular time $t = t_p$.

To study the deformation of the sheet caused by the change in moisture content, the variation of the total potential energy is used. This is done by allowing variations of the four displacement coefficients a , b , c , and d in Eq. (15). Equating the first variation to zero results in four nonlinear equilibrium equations of the form

$$f_a(a, b, c, d) = 0 \quad f_b(a, b, c, d) = 0 \quad f_c(a, b, c, d) = 0 \quad f_d(a, b, c, d) = 0. \quad (16)$$

Solving these equations for a particular time $t = t_p$ gives the configuration of the sheet as it is subjected to a transient change in moisture content. The stability of the configuration is assessed by examining the second variation of the total potential energy. The overall procedure has been implemented using *MATHEMATICA*[®].

2.3. Numerical results

In this section the developed model is used to study the response of a paper sheet subjected to transient moisture diffusion. The sheet has a square shape with a 0.1 m-side length ($L_x = L_y = 0.1$ m) and is composed of three layers. The properties of these layers are given in Table 1. Since the layers have different properties, the sheet is unsymmetric relative to its midplane. Initially, the sheet is flat and has a uniform moisture content (M_o) of 14% which corresponds to ambient air at 75% relative

humidity (RH_0). Suddenly, a 10.8%-moisture content (M_∞) is applied to the outer surfaces which corresponds to air at 50% relative humidity (RH_∞). The convective mass transfer coefficient at the two outer surfaces was evaluated at $5.39 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}\%$ using equations given in Siau [7]. During the moisture diffusion process the sheet develops curvature. The objective is to demonstrate the ability of the model to predict the moisture content distribution through the thickness of the sheet and the induced deformation as a function of time during the diffusion process. The predictions are validated with finite-element analyses performed with ABAQUS.

Table 1 Properties of the three-layer paper sheet

Layer	h (mm)	ρ (kg/m ³)	E_x (GPa)	E_y (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	ν_{yx}	β_x (10 ⁻³ /%)	β_y (10 ⁻³ /%)	D (10 ⁻¹¹ m ² /s)
1	0.100	448	4.41	2.01	1.04	0.12	0.46	1.38	6.90
2	0.132	343	3.09	1.02	0.59	0.12	0.38	1.57	13.92
3	0.115	535	4.04	4.04	1.46	0.27	0.56	0.56	7.73

Fig. 2 Transient moisture content distribution for a three-layer paper sheet

First, the developed model determines the distribution of the moisture content in the three-layer paper sheet as a function of time. Figure 2 shows the through-thickness moisture content distribution predicted by Eq. (7) at different times. The dashed lines correspond to results from finite-element analyses. At $t = 0$, moisture content is supposed to be constant and equal to 14%. Some deviations between the expected and approximate solution can be observed since a very large number of terms in the series solution is required to approximate a straight line. However, for larger times the predicted moisture content distribution is expected to be more accurate. As time increases, the moisture content in the sheet decreases. At $t = 3600 \text{ s}$, steady state equilibrium is reached and the moisture content is constant and equal to 10.8%. As can be observed, the moisture content distributions computed by the present model correlate

well with the finite-element predictions once the first second is passed. For $0 < t < 1$ s, the number of terms used in the series solution is not large enough to accurately predict the moisture content near the outer surfaces of the sheet. However, the present model quite accurately predicts the moisture content in the sheet away from the outer surfaces.

Next, at different particular times the moisture content distribution is approximated using the piecewise-linear function. The number of intervals used in the approximation is $J = 6$ (for each layer).

Finally, the deformation induced by the moisture content change predicted by the piecewise-linear function is computed. The results are presented in Fig. 3 in the form of curvatures in the x - and y -directions, i.e. $(-a)$, $(-b)$ versus time. The dashed lines represented in the figures correspond to results from finite-element analyses. Referring to the figures, at $t = 0$, the curvatures are zero since the sheet is initially flat. As soon as the moisture diffusion starts, the curvature in the y -direction suddenly increases. The curvature in the x -direction remains zero through the diffusion process. Therefore, the sheet takes a cylindrical shape with its generator parallel to the x -axis. As time increases, the curvature keeps increasing but at a slower rate. Steady state equilibrium is reached at $t = 3600$ s. As observed in the figure, the curvatures determined by the finite-element analysis correlate well with the ones predicted by the present model.

Fig. 3 Curvatures of paper sheet versus time ($L_x = L_y = 0.1$ m)

4. CASE STUDY

Gendron et al. [2] studied the steady-state response of two cardboard layups subjected to a uniform change in moisture content. They used a model based on the approach proposed by Hyer [3] and a geometrically non linear finite-element model. The results showed that both models provide very similar results and that different equilibrium shapes can be obtained depending on the type of cardboard, moisture content change, and sheet dimension. For the first cardboard layup, called NPB, both models predict that the final configuration was cylindrical with a generator parallel to the x -axis. For the second cardboard layup, called PB, the final configuration predicted by the finite-element model was also cylindrical but with a generator parallel to the y -axis.

The developed model was used to study the transient response of the two cardboard layups subjected to a 5%-moisture content change. The objective of the analyses is to study the ability of the developed model to predict the occurrence of multiple equilibrium configurations as a function of time. Only the results obtained for the NPB cardboard layup will be presented and discussed here since they were the most interesting.

Properties for the NPB cardboard layers are given in Table 2. The convective mass transfer coefficient was assumed to be equal to 3.2×10^{-4} kg/m²s% at the two outer surfaces [8]. The cardboard piece was square with a 0.3 m-side length. The results of the transient model and finite-element analyses are presented in Fig. 4.

Table 2 Properties of the NPB cardboard

Layer	h (mm)	ρ (kg/m ³)	E_x (GPa)	E_y (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	ν_{yx}	β_x (10 ⁻³ /%)	β_y (10 ⁻³ /%)	D (10 ⁻¹¹ m ² /s)
1	0.059	1034	7.1	1.3	2.19	0.16	0.14	1.72	5.7
2	0.405	548	1.8	0.6	0.98	0.09	0.30	1.34	5.7
3	0.042	857	7.5	1.7	1.58	0.15	0.28	1.94	5.7

Figure 4 shows the curvatures in the x - and y -directions as a function of time for the NPB cardboard. For $0 < t < 0.28$ s, curvature κ_x rapidly increases in magnitude whereas curvature κ_y first increases and then decreases to approach zero. There is only one solution, denoted (1) in the figure. From $t = 0.28$ s, two other solutions appear and remain present until steady-state equilibrium is reached. These solutions are denoted (2) and (3) in the graphs. When steady-state equilibrium is reached, solution (1) corresponds to a cylindrical shape with a generator parallel to the y -axis whereas solution (2) corresponds to a cylindrical shape with a generator parallel to the x -axis. Solution (3) corresponds to a shallow bowl shape. A stability analysis shows that the bowl shape (3) is unstable and that the two cylindrical shapes (1) and (2) are stable. Shape (1) presents the lowest potential energy and should correspond to the actual

equilibrium state. As observed in the figure, the finite-element predictions follow solution (1) obtained with the developed model quite closely.

The predictions obtained with the transient analyses can be compared to the ones obtained with the steady-state analyses by Gendron et al. [2]. For the NPB cardboard, the steady state analysis predicted that the shape was cylindrical with a generator parallel to the x -axis. Curiously, the transient analyses predict that the shape is cylindrical but with a generator parallel to the y -axis. Although surprising, this result is very interesting. It indicates that to adequately predict the hygro-mechanical deformation in a multi-layer paper or cardboard sheet the transient diffusion of moisture through the sheet thickness needs to be taken into account.

Fig. 4 Curvatures versus time for the NPB cardboard

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A model has been proposed to study the transient response of multi-layer sheets made of paper or cardboard subjected to moisture diffusion through the thickness. The model predicts the through-thickness moisture content distribution as a function of time. From these results, the moisture-induced deformation can be determined for different time

values. The model was used to study the behaviour of three-layer paper and cardboard sheets. Finite-element analyses were also performed to validate the model predictions. Comparison between the predictions from the present model and the finite-element analyses demonstrate that the model can quite accurately predict the deformation behaviour of sheets subjected to transient moisture diffusion.

The predictions obtained for the cardboard sheet were compared to predictions previously obtained using steady-state analyses. The comparison revealed important differences in the shapes predicted for the cardboard sheet. This result suggests that the moisture diffusion process may influence the configuration assumed by a sheet at steady-state equilibrium. Therefore, it is necessary to take the moisture diffusion in the analysis into account to accurately predict the hygro-mechanical behaviour of paper or cardboard sheets.

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